

Analytical Study of the Thermal Conductivity and Resistivity Properties of Zig-Zag Single-Walled (8,0) Carbon Nanotube Using Deng-Fan-Hulthen Potential Model

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Abstract: This work presents an analytical investigation of the thermal conductivity and thermal resistivity of a zig-zag single-walled (8,0) carbon nanotube using the Deng–Fan–Hulthén potential model. In the presence of magnetic and Aharonov–Bohm (AB) flux fields, the Schrödinger wave equation is solved using the Nikiforov–Uvarov (NU) method, from which the energy eigenvalue and eigenfunction equations are obtained. The partition function is then derived and used to evaluate the thermal conductivity and resistivity properties of the nanotube. Graphical analyses are carried out to examine the variation of energy values with magnetic field strength and Aharonov–Bohm flux. In addition, plots of thermal conductivity against temperature and bond length are presented, while the variation of thermal resistivity with temperature is also examined. The results show that both the magnetic field and AB flux field have a positive influence on the energy values, causing them to increase exponentially. Similarly, thermal conductivity increases with temperature and bond length. However, thermal resistivity decreases exponentially with temperature, thereby confirming the semiconducting nature of the zig-zag single-walled (8,0) carbon nanotube.

Keywords: Deng-Fan-Hulthen Potential; Magnetic Field; Aharonov-Bohm flux field; Thermal Conductivity; Thermal Resistivity; Nikiforov-Uvarov method.

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Introduction

Further miniaturization of microelectronic components like transistors into computer chips may become impossible in the near future due to the fundamental laws of physics that governs the principle of operations of transistors manufactured or fabricated from silicon which may elicit some technical problems in the areas of power consumption, heat and current leakage. Consequent upon this, there is the need to search for new materials whose properties or features are well suited to address these problems being envisaged by the current silicon based technology (Anjum, 2008; Novoselov *et al.*,2004). And one material that is seen as a potential replacement for silicon based transistors is carbon nanotubes (CNTs). CNTs are seen as one of the strongest materials with very high elasticity, high conductivity, miniature in size with good stability and their robust nature allow them to withstand chemically hostile

environments. This miniature nature and their high surface area make them suitable candidates for the attachment and assembly of nanoparticles (NPs) on their surface. Their electrical, magnetic and even their physical properties can be improved significantly when either their internal cavity or external surface are decorated with different inorganic NPs using various experimental procedures (Ado *et al.*,2008; Kim & Rina, 2011).

Carbon nanotubes are sheets of graphene rolled around a central axis, forming hollow cylindrical shapes. CNTs are in two types-single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) and multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) (Hosseini *et al.*,2020). Due to the small nanoscale diameter, the confinement and movement of electrons is along their length, hence, CNTs are regarded as 1D nanomaterials (Philip & Deji, 2011). The SWCNTs are rolled-up cylindrical sheets of graphene made up of benzene type hexagonal

network of carbon atoms that are sp^2 hybridized. Their diameters are in the range of 1 to 2 nanometer with lengths of several micrometer to centimeters. MWCNTs are made up of layers of graphene sheets rolled-up to form a concentric tubular shape. They can be regarded as arrays of concentric SWCNTs stacked in between each other with a spacing of about 0.34 nanometer Saifuddin *et al.*, 2013; Sabastien *et al.*, 2013.

Single-walled carbon nanotubes can be metallic or semiconducting in behavior based on their stacking or arrangement of the carbon atoms or their structural features and chirality Phaedon *et al.*, 2003; Francis, 2023). In determining the electronic properties of carbon nanotubes, similar reasons or more have been given by various authors on the metallic or semiconducting nature of CNTs. For instance, the manner in which the graphene sheet is rolled up to form determines the metallic or semiconducting behavior of single-walled carbon nanotubes. From the aspect of the diameter, a nanotube of a particular diameter is categorized into metallic, small band-gap semiconductor and moderate band gap semiconductor respectively (Morkoc, 2003). Ebbesen *et al.*, (1996), attributed the metallic or semiconducting nature of carbon nanotubes to their diameter and helicity of the carbon atoms in the nanotubes shells. In their experimental work, four-probe measurements were done on single nanotubes prepared by different methods. A comparison of various samples were done from the samples of two-probe measurements. They measured the various samples in terms of the electrical conductivities and resistivities with respect to temperature. From their findings, single nanotubes having a diameter of the likelihood of thirty nanometer (30nm) could exhibit metallic or semiconducting behavior based on helicity. They suggested that the semiconducting nanotubes should be having diameters of up to thirty nanometer (30nm). However, the geometrical differences and structural defects were not ruled out in the electrical or electronic properties of the carbon nanotubes. In fact the electronic properties of CNTs have been reported to be

highly influenced by the geometric differences like defects, chirality, different diameters etc (Khalid, 2013). Skâkalova and co-authors mentioned the type of the single-walled carbon nanotubes coupled with the experimental configuration and condition of emergence determine the electronic transport properties of single-walled carbon nanotubes individually (Skâkalova *et al.*, 2006). In establishing both the metallic and the semiconducting features of single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs), Dass and Vaid carried out a study analytically on the chirality dependence of electronic band structure and density of states. Their results were compared with simulated values and the metallic and semiconducting nature of SWCNTs was affirmed. From their reports, all armchair SWCNTs showed metallic behavior while zig-zag SWCNTs exhibited both metallic and semiconducting features (Devi & Rakesh, 2017). The Aharonov-Bohm (AB) phase created around cylindrical nanotube in a magnetic field parallel to its axis alters the band structure. A metallic CNT can be transformed into a semiconducting CNT and semiconducting tube can become metallic due to the effect of applied magnetic field. This situation results in unusual behavior of magnetoresistance (Ado *et al.*, 2008; Ovchinnikov & Atrazhov, 1998). Also, the presence of magnetic field can alter the electrical properties of carbon nanotubes. For instance, semiconducting carbon nanotubes are could be transformed into metallic CNTs when placed inside magnetic field. The presence of magnetic field causes the band gap of semiconducting nanotubes to shrink (Sanjay, 2007). Michael reported how the magnetic field affects the metallicity of CNTs. According to them, CNTs that are metallic can become semiconductors CNTs by the application of minute external magnetic field parallel to the tubes. CNTs that are semiconducting can be made metallic under ultra-high magnetic field (Michael, 2006). CNTs are very good thermal conductors and can withstand high temperatures. The strong carbon-carbon chemical bonding account for their high thermal conductivity. When compared to copper wire, CNTs can transmit

over 15 times the amount of energy (Sonia and Nazmul, 2018; Anjum, 2008). The thermal conductivity of aligned bundles of SWNTs is reported to be greater than 200 W/mk at room temperature. Thermal conductivity of CNTs gives us useful insight about the low-energy phonon structure of nanotubes [3]. Thermal conductivity, k , of a substance or material is a consequence of the transportation of energy through electrons or through lattice vibrations (phonons) (Angus, 2008). This high thermal conductivity is being utilized in the design and development of heat removal devices that are CNTs-based to help dissipate heat generated by integrated circuits (ICs) (Ado *et al.*, 2008). CNTs can exhibit a temperature-dependent resistivity when under the influence of thermal energy. This phenomenon is referred to as thermo resistivity of CNT. Thermo resistivity refers to as the electrical resistance response of a material to changes in temperature difference. For single-walled carbon nanotubes that are semiconducting in nature, their thermo resistivity is negative. That is the electrical resistivity decreases with increase in temperature. Metallic single-walled carbon nanotube has positive thermo resistivity whose electrical resistivity increases with temperature increase (Francis, 2023).

In the bid to search for a material whose device applications can be miniaturized and as well perform optimally, we intend to study analytically with Deng-Fan-Hulthen potential the thermal conductivity and resistivity properties of zig-zag single-walled (8,0) carbon nanotube in the presence of magnetic and Ahanorov-Bohm (AB) flux fields. Zig-zag single-walled (8,0) carbon nanotube has a length of $6.403(\text{\AA})$ and symmetry group, P4/mmm (Constantinos *et al.*, 2019). The density of state at the Fermi

$$\frac{1}{2\mu} (i\hbar\vec{\nabla} - \frac{q}{c}\vec{A})^2 + D_e \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{(e^{\lambda r} - 1)}\right)^2 - \frac{V_0 e^{\lambda r}}{(1 - e^{-\lambda r})} = E_{(n,m)} \psi_{(\rho,\varphi,z)} \quad (1)$$

where $\eta = e^{\lambda r_e} - 1$, D_e represents the dissociation energy, r_e stands for the molecular bond length, r is the internuclear distance, λ , is the range of the potential well and V_0 stands for the potential strength (Ikot *et al.*, 2021).

Here, μ , is taken to be the effective mass for single-walled carbon nanotube. The vector potential \vec{A}

energy is zero depicting its semiconducting nature. It has a calculated band gap of 1.360 eV and a simulated band gap of 1.4078 eV respectively. The total number of unit cells and carbon atoms in the overall unit cells are 16 and 32 respectively. In its molecular structure, the total number of unit cells, carbon atoms and hexagons are 208, 416 and 192 (Davi & Rakesh, 2017; Devi *et al.*, 2012).

The Deng-Fan-Hulthen potential consists of two different potentials-Deng-Fan and Hulthen potentials which can be used to study molecular systems. The radial part of the Schrödinger wave equation will be solved analytically with the Nikiforov-Uvarov (NU) method to obtain the energy equation and the wave function. The partition function will be calculated to enable us determine the thermal conductivity and resistivity of zig-zag single-walled (8,0) carbon nanotube.

The organization of this paper is as follows; in section 2, the quantum Hamiltonian of a charged particle placed in our potential under the combined influence of an external magnetic field B and Ahanorov-Bohm (AB) flux where the Schrödinger wave equation is solved analytically is considered. The partition function used to evaluate the thermodynamic properties of conductivity and resistivity is calculated in section 3. Our results and discussion are done in section 4. The conclusion is done in the last section followed by the references.

Theoretical Model and Formulation

In the cylindrical co-ordinate system, we write the quantum Hamiltonian of a charge particle kept in a region Deng-Fan-Hulthen potential) under the combined influence of an external magnetic field B and Ahanorov-Bohm (AB) flux as:

is written as the summation of two terms, $\vec{A} = \vec{A}_1 + \vec{A}_2$ and $\nabla \times \vec{A}_1 = \vec{B}$ and $\nabla \times \vec{A}_2 = 0$ is the symmetric or Coulomb gauge. B_z is the applied magnetic field along the z-direction. The additional magnetic flux Φ_{AB} is due to a solenoid. So, in the cylindrical coordinate system, the vector potential has the azimuthal components written as (Sameer et al,2014):

$$\vec{A}_1 = \frac{\vec{B}e^{-\theta r}}{(1-e^{-\theta r})}, \vec{A}_2 = \frac{\Phi_{AB}}{2\pi r} \hat{\Phi}. \text{ So, } \vec{A} = \left(0, \frac{\vec{B}e^{-\theta r}}{(1-e^{-\theta r})} + \frac{\Phi_{AB}}{2\pi r}, 0\right) \quad (2)$$

The Deng-Fan-Hulthen Potential which is our confining potential is a combination of two different potentials-Deng-Fan and Hulthen potentials. Below is the graphical behavior of the potential model.

Fig. 1 Deng-Fan-Hulthen Potential graphical behaviour

In the cylindrical coordinates our wave function is taken as:

$$\psi_{(r,\varphi)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{im\varphi} U_{nm}(r) \quad m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2 \dots \quad (3)$$

where m represents the magnetic quantum number. By inserting our potential, vector potential and the wave function into Eq. (1), a second order differential equation of the form will be obtained:

$$\frac{d^2 U_{nm}(r)}{dr^2} + \frac{2\mu}{\hbar^2} \left[E - D_e \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{(e^{\lambda r} - 1)} \right)^2 + \frac{V_0 e^{-\lambda r}}{(1 - e^{-\lambda r})} - \frac{2\hbar m e \lambda \vec{B} e^{-\lambda r}}{c(1 - e^{-\lambda r})} - \frac{e^2 \vec{B} e^{-2\lambda r}}{c^2(1 - e^{-\lambda r})^2} - \frac{e^2 \vec{B} \Phi_{AB} e^{-\lambda r}}{c^2(1 - e^{-\lambda r})^2 2\pi r} - \frac{((m + \zeta) - \frac{1}{4})}{r^2} \right] U_{nm}(r) = 0 \quad (4)$$

Since this differential equation contains both exponential and radial terms and improved approximation scheme by Greene and Aldrich, given in the equation below will help to solve the equation (Ikot et al.,2021).

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \approx \lambda^2 \left[d_0 + \frac{e^{-\lambda r}}{(1 - e^{-\lambda r})^2} \right] \quad (5)$$

By inserting Eq. (5) into Eq. (4) we have

$$\frac{d^2 U_{nm}(r)}{dr^2} + \left[\frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2} - \frac{2\mu D_e}{\hbar^2} + \frac{4\mu D_e \eta e^{-\lambda r}}{\hbar^2(1 - e^{-\lambda r})} + \frac{2D_e \eta^2 e^{-2\lambda r}}{\hbar^2(1 - e^{-\lambda r})^2} + \frac{2V_0 e^{-\lambda r}}{\hbar^2(1 - e^{-\lambda r})} - \frac{2m\eta \lambda \vec{B} e^{-\lambda r}}{\hbar^2(1 - e^{-\lambda r})^2} - \frac{\eta^2 \vec{B}^2 e^{-2\lambda r}}{\hbar^2(1 - e^{-\lambda r})^2} - \frac{\eta^2 \lambda \vec{B} \Phi_{AB} e^{-\lambda r}}{\hbar^2(1 - e^{-\lambda r})^2 \pi} - \frac{((m + \zeta) - \frac{1}{4})\lambda^2 \left(d_0 + \frac{e^{-\lambda r}}{(1 - e^{-\lambda r})^2} \right)}{4} \right] U_{nm}(r) = 0 \quad (6)$$

Where $\eta = \frac{e}{c}$, $\Phi_0 = \frac{\hbar c}{e}$, $\zeta = \frac{\Phi_{AB}}{\Phi_0}$ and $\eta = e^{\theta r} - 1$, c is the speed of light.

$$\text{Using the transformation } z = e^{-\lambda r} \quad (7)$$

After differentiating twice, you will obtain:

$$\frac{d^2}{dz^2} = \frac{\lambda^2 z^2 d^2}{dz^2} + \frac{\lambda^2 z d}{dz} \quad (8)$$

Substituting Eq. (8) into Eq. (6) and divide through by $\lambda^2 z^2$ the result will be:

$$\frac{d^2 U_{nm}}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{z} \frac{dU_{nm}}{dz} + \frac{1}{z^2} \left[\frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2 \lambda^2} - \frac{2\mu D_e}{\hbar^2 \lambda^2} + \frac{4\mu D_e \eta z}{\hbar^2 \lambda^2 (1-z)} - \frac{2\mu D_e \eta^2 z^2}{\hbar^2 \lambda^2 (1-z)^2} + \frac{2\mu V_o z}{\hbar^2 \lambda^2 (1-z)} - \frac{2m\eta \bar{B} z}{\hbar \lambda (1-z)^2} - \frac{\eta^2 \bar{B}^2 z^2}{\hbar^2 \lambda (1-z)^2} - \frac{\eta^2 \bar{B} \Phi_{AB} z}{\hbar^2 \lambda (1-z)^2 \pi} - \left((m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \right) \left(d_o + \frac{z}{(1-z)^2} \right) \right] U_{nm}(r) = 0 \quad (9)$$

We use the following dimensionless symbols for mathematical convenience

$$-\varepsilon = \frac{2\mu(E_{nm} - D_e)}{\hbar^2 \lambda^2}, \quad \gamma_1 = \frac{4\mu D_e \eta}{\hbar^2 \lambda^2}, \quad \gamma_2 = \frac{2\mu D_e \eta^2}{\hbar^2 \lambda^2}, \quad d_o = \frac{2\mu V_o}{\hbar^2 \lambda^2}, \quad \chi = \frac{2m\eta \bar{B}}{\hbar \lambda}, \quad \lambda_1 = \frac{\eta^2 \bar{B}^2}{\hbar^2 \lambda^2}, \quad \lambda_2 = \frac{\eta^2 \bar{B} \Phi_{AB}}{\hbar^2 \lambda^2 \pi}, \quad V = \left((m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \right) \quad (10)$$

Equation (9) can be rewritten with respect to these dimensionless symbols as:

$$\frac{d^2 U_{nm}}{dz^2} + \frac{(1-z)}{z(1-z)} \frac{dU_{nm}}{dz} + \frac{1}{z^2(1-z)^2} [-\varepsilon(1-z)^2 + \gamma_1(1-z)z - \gamma_2(z^2) + d_o(1-z)z - \chi(z) - \lambda_1(z^2) - \lambda_2(1-z)z - Vd_o(1-z)^2 - V(z)] U_{nm} = 0 \quad (11)$$

Subsequently, Eq. (11) can be evaluated further as:

$$\frac{d^2 U_{nm}}{dz^2} + \frac{(1-z)}{z(1-z)} \frac{dU_{nm}}{dz} + \frac{1}{z^2(1-z)^2} [-(\varepsilon + \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 + d_o + \lambda_1 - \lambda_2 + Vd_o)z^2 + (2\varepsilon + \gamma_1 + d_o - \chi - \lambda_2 + 2Vd_o - V)z - (\varepsilon + Vd_o)] U_{nm} = 0 \quad (12)$$

Equation (12) is compared with the parametric form of the NU of Eq. (13) is written as (Otete and Eleje, 2023)

$$R''(z) + \frac{\gamma_1 - \gamma_2 z}{z(1-\gamma_3 z)} R'(z) + \left[\frac{-\xi_1 z^2 + \xi_2 z - \xi_3}{z^2(1-\gamma_3 z)^2} \right] R(z) = 0 \quad (13)$$

The energy eigen values equation according to the NU is written as

$$\gamma_2 n - (2n+1)\gamma_5 + (2n+1) [\sqrt{\gamma_9} + \gamma_3 \sqrt{\gamma_8}] + n(n-1)\gamma_3 + \gamma_7 + 2\gamma_3 \gamma_8 + 2\sqrt{\gamma_8 \gamma_9} = 0 \quad (14)$$

The corresponding wave function is given as:

$$U_{nm}(z) = z^{\gamma_{12}} (1 - \gamma_3 z)^{-\gamma_{12} - \gamma_{13}/\gamma_3} p_n^{\gamma_{10-1} \left(\frac{\gamma_{11}}{\gamma_3} \right) - (\gamma_{10-1})} (1 - 2\gamma_3 z) \quad (15)$$

where the following parameters are written as

$$\gamma_4 = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \gamma_1) \quad (16)$$

$$\gamma_5 = \frac{1}{2}(\gamma_2 - 2\gamma_3) \quad (17)$$

$$\gamma_6 = \gamma_5 + \xi_1 \quad (18)$$

$$\gamma_7 = 2\gamma_4 \gamma_5 - \xi_2 \quad (19)$$

$$\gamma_8 = \gamma_4^2 + \xi_3 \quad (20)$$

$$\gamma_9 = \gamma_3 \gamma_7 + \gamma_3^2 \gamma_8 + \gamma_6 \quad (21)$$

$$\gamma_{10} = \gamma_1 + 2\gamma_4 + 2\sqrt{\gamma_8} \quad (22)$$

$$\gamma_{11} = \gamma_2 - 2\gamma_5 + 2(\sqrt{\gamma_9} + \gamma_3\sqrt{\gamma_8}) \quad (23)$$

$$\gamma_{12} = \gamma_4 + \sqrt{\gamma_8} \quad (24)$$

$$\gamma_{13} = \gamma_5 - (\sqrt{\gamma_9} + \gamma_3\sqrt{\gamma_8}) \quad (25)$$

When Eq. (12) is compared with the parametric form of the NU of Eq. (13) the following parameters can be found:

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = \gamma_3 = 1 \quad (26)$$

$$\xi_1 = \varepsilon + \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 + d_b + \lambda_1 - \lambda_2 + Vd_o \quad (27)$$

$$\xi_2 = 2\varepsilon + \gamma_1 + d_b - \chi - \lambda_2 + 2Vd_o - V \quad (28)$$

$$\xi_3 = \varepsilon + Vd_o \quad (29)$$

From Eqs. (16-21) we obtain

$$\gamma_4 = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \gamma_1) = 0, \gamma_5 = \frac{1}{2}(\gamma_2 - 2\gamma_3) = -\frac{1}{2}, \gamma_6 = \gamma_5^2 + \xi_1 = \frac{1}{4} + \varepsilon + \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 + d_b + \lambda_1 - \lambda_2 + Vd_o \quad (30)$$

$$\gamma_7 = 2\gamma_4\gamma_5 - \xi_2 = -(2\varepsilon + \gamma_1 + d_b - \chi - \lambda_2 + 2Vd_o - V) \quad (31)$$

$$\gamma_8 = \gamma_4^2 + \xi_3 = \varepsilon + Vd_o \quad (32)$$

$$\gamma_9 = \gamma_3\gamma_7 + \gamma_3^2\gamma_8 + \gamma_6 = \frac{1}{4} + \chi + V + \lambda_1 + \gamma_2 \quad (33)$$

$$\text{Recall that in Eq. (10), } -\varepsilon = \frac{2\mu(E_{nm} - D_e)}{\hbar^2\lambda^2} \quad (34)$$

So, substituting Eqs. (30-33) into Eq. (14) and carrying out some algebra the energy eigenvalue equation of the Deng-Fan-Hulthen potential is obtained as:

$$E_{nm} = -\frac{\hbar^2\lambda^2}{2\mu} \left[\left(\frac{(\sigma - \Lambda)}{2(\tau + \sqrt{\sigma})} - \frac{(\tau + \sqrt{\sigma})}{2} \right)^2 - Vd_o + D_e \right] \quad (35)$$

Where

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{4} + \chi + V + \lambda_1 + \gamma_2, \Lambda = -\gamma_1 - d_b + \chi + \lambda_2 + V, \tau = n + \frac{1}{2} \quad (36)$$

Thus, Eq. (36) can be re-written in terms of the dimensionless symbols of Eq. (10) as:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{4} + \frac{2m\eta\bar{B}}{\hbar\lambda} + (m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{\eta^2\bar{B}^2}{\hbar^2\lambda^2} + \frac{2\mu D_e \eta^2}{\hbar^2\lambda^2} \quad (37)$$

$$\Lambda = -\frac{4\mu D_e \eta}{\hbar^2\lambda^2} - \frac{2\mu V_o}{\hbar^2\lambda^2} + \frac{2m\eta\bar{B}}{\hbar\lambda} + \frac{\eta^2\bar{B}\Phi_{AB}}{\hbar^2\lambda\pi} + (m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \quad (38)$$

From Eqs. (22-25) we determine

$$\gamma_{10} = \gamma_1 + 2\gamma_4 + 2\sqrt{\gamma_8} = 1 + 2\sqrt{\varepsilon + Vd_o} \quad (39)$$

$$\gamma_{11} = \gamma_2 - 2\gamma_5 + 2(\sqrt{\gamma_9} + \gamma_3\sqrt{\gamma_8}) = 2 + 2\left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{4} + \chi + V + \lambda_1 + \gamma_2 + \varepsilon + Vd_o}\right) \quad (40)$$

$$\gamma_{12} = \gamma_4 + \sqrt{\gamma_8} = \sqrt{\varepsilon + Vd_o} \quad (41)$$

$$\gamma_{13} = \gamma_5 - (\sqrt{\gamma_9} + \gamma_3\sqrt{\gamma_8}) = -\frac{1}{2} - \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{4} + \chi + V + \lambda_1 + \gamma_2} + \sqrt{\varepsilon + Vd_0} \right) \quad (42)$$

Substituting Eqs. (39-42) into Eq. (15) the wave function written in Eq. (43) is obtained.

$$U_{nm}(z) = z^{\sqrt{\varepsilon+Vd_0}}(1-z)^{\frac{1}{2}+\sqrt{\frac{1}{4}+\chi+V+\lambda_1+\gamma_2}} P_n^{2\sqrt{\varepsilon+Vd_0}, 2\sqrt{\frac{1}{4}+\chi+V+\lambda_1+\gamma_2}}(1-2z) \quad (43)$$

The Partition Function and the Thermodynamic Properties of Carbon Nanotube

Thermal conductivity and resistivity are two aspects of the thermodynamic properties of nanotubes that can be determined. In order to calculate these two properties, the partition function which is temperature dependent is first evaluated. At a given temperature, when a direct summation is done over all possible energy levels, the partition function can be evaluated. The partition function is written as (Ikot *et al.*, 2020):

$$Z(\beta) = \sum_n^{v_{max}} e^{-\beta E_{n,m}} \quad (44)$$

where $\beta = \frac{1}{KT}$ with K as the Boltzmann constant, T , the temperature E_{nm} is the energy of the n th bound state where $n = 0, 1, 2, 3 \dots, v_{max}$.

The energy eigen value of equation (35) can be re-written as:

$$E_{nm} = -\hbar^2\lambda^2 \left(\frac{N_1 - (n+\sigma)^2}{2(n+\sigma)} \right)^2 + N_2 \quad (45)$$

$$N_1 = \frac{1}{4} + \frac{2m\eta\bar{B}}{\hbar\lambda} + (m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{\eta^2\bar{B}^2}{\hbar^2\lambda^2} + \frac{2\mu D_e\eta^2}{\hbar^2\lambda^2} + \frac{4\mu D_e\eta}{\hbar^2\lambda^2} - \frac{2\mu V_0}{\hbar^2\lambda^2} + \frac{2m\eta\bar{B}}{\hbar\lambda} + \frac{\eta^2\bar{B}\Phi_{AB}}{\hbar^2\lambda\pi} + (m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \quad (46)$$

Where

$$N_2 = \left((m + \zeta)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \right) d_o \left(\frac{\hbar^2\lambda^2}{2\mu} \right) + D_e \quad (47)$$

Therefore, equation (44) can be recast as:

$$Z(\beta) = \sum_n^{v_{max}} e^{-\beta \left[-\frac{\hbar^2\lambda^2(N_1 - (n+\sigma)^2)^2}{2\mu} + N_2 \right]} \quad (48)$$

In the classical limit, the summation of equation (48) is replaced by an integral therefore we have

$$Z(\beta) = \int_0^v e^{(Pl^2\beta + \frac{G\beta}{l^2} + M\beta)} dl, l = n + \sigma \quad (49)$$

Where

$$P = \frac{\hbar^2\lambda^2}{8\mu}, G = -\frac{\hbar^2\lambda^2 N_1^2}{8\mu}, M = -\left(\frac{\hbar^2\lambda^2 N_1}{4\mu} + N_2 \right) \quad (50)$$

The Maple software is used to evaluate equation (49) to obtain the partition function of the system as:

$$\frac{1}{2} e^{P\beta.l^2 + M\beta} \sqrt{G\beta} \left(\frac{2v.e^{\frac{G\beta}{v^2}}}{\sqrt{G\beta}} - \frac{2\sqrt{G\beta} \sqrt{\pi} \operatorname{erfi}\left(\frac{G\beta}{v}\right)}{\sqrt{G\beta}} - 2\sqrt{\pi} \right) \quad (51)$$

Where $\text{erfi}(k)$ denotes the imaginary error function (Edet *et al.*,2020) define as

$$\text{erfi}(k) = i\text{erf}(k) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^k e^{t^2} dt \quad (52)$$

In Maple software, this error function is used for various numerical calculations.

With the partition function of the system known, the thermal conductivity K , which is a function of heat capacity, phonon group velocity and the free mean path. The thermal conductivity of CNTs can be written as (Michael & Jang-Yu, 2009) :

$$K = \frac{1}{3} \rho c v^2 \tau_s \quad (53)$$

Here, c , v , and τ represent specific heat per unit volume, group velocity and relaxation time or free mean path of a given phonon state respectively (Bounphanh, 2011). The specific heat capacity is given by the relation (Khordad & Rastegar, 2017):

$$\text{Specific heat } C_v = \frac{\partial U}{\partial T} = k_B \beta^2 \frac{\partial^2 \ln Z}{\partial \beta^2} \quad (54)$$

So we can write the thermal conductivity as:

$$\text{Thermal conductivity } K = \frac{1}{3} \rho v^2 \tau_s k_B \beta^2 \frac{\partial^2 \ln Z}{\partial \beta^2} \quad (55)$$

The thermal resistivity is obtained from the inverse of thermal conductivity of Eq. (55).

We present the graphical plots of energy variation with magnetic field and Aharonov-Bohm (AB) flux in figures 2 and 3 respectively.

Fig. 2: Plot of Energy, E versus magnetic field B

Fig. 3: Plot of Energy, E versus AB flux

We present the graphical plots of the thermal conductivity with temperature variation and bond length in figure 4 and 5.

Fig. 4: Plot of thermal conductivity versus temperature

Fig. 5 Plot of thermal conductivity versus bond length

Here is the graphical plot of thermal resistivity versus temperature

Fig. 6: Plot of thermal resistivity versus temperature

Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows the plot of the energy, E with varying magnetic field \vec{B} at different values of the AB flux. It can be seen that the energy values shows exponential rise as the magnetic field strength increases. Figure 3 depicts the plot of the energy E against Aharonov-Bohm (AB) flux Φ_{AB} for the respective values of $0.1T$, $0.2T$ and $0.3T$ of the magnetic field strength. As the AB flux increases exponentially, the energy values increase correspondingly. So, the notable impact both fields have in the increment of the energy values can be seen. In figure 4, the plot of thermal conductivity with temperature variations is shown, from the plot, the values of the thermal conductivity show exponential increase with the temperature. The phonon scattering accounts for this behavior. The thermal conductivity versus the bond length is shown in figure 5. The thermal conductivity increases exponentially as the bond length increases. This phenomenon is as a result of the increase in the thermal transport which varies proportionally with the SWCNT bond length. Also, the phonons wavelength that serve as medium for thermal transport increases as the bond length increases. In figure 6, the plot of thermal resistivity with the temperature is shown. It is seen that the thermal resistivity decreases as the temperature is increasing. The reason is that as the concentration of the thermally generated electron-hole pairs increases, the thermal resistivity of our zig-zag single-walled (8,0) decreases with the increasing temperature. The carrier scattering on

phonons also accounts for this phenomenon or behavior. This graphical behavior of figure 6 tells us that zig-zag single-walled (8,0) is semiconducting in nature.

Conclusion

The analytical solution for the energy eigenvalues of the Schrödinger wave equation with the Deng–Fan–Hulthén potential was obtained using the Nikiforov–Uvarov method. The effects of magnetic and Aharonov–Bohm (AB) flux fields on the energy eigenvalues were analysed graphically. The results revealed that the energy eigenvalues increased exponentially with both fields. The calculated partition function was further used to evaluate the thermodynamic properties of the nanotube, particularly thermal conductivity and thermal resistivity, as functions of temperature and bond length. The thermal conductivity of the nanotube increased exponentially with both temperature and bond length, whereas the thermal resistivity decreased exponentially with temperature. As shown in Figure 6, the zig-zag SWCNT (8,0) exhibited semiconducting behaviour, which agrees with the findings of Davi and Rakesh (2017). Thus, this semiconducting SWCNT could serve as a promising material for the fabrication of high-performance field-effect transistors (FETs) in the electronics industry. In addition, its favourable thermal conductivity suggests potential application in the thermal management systems of thermoelectric materials.

Statements and Declaration

Authors Contributions

Ikechukwu Otete: Conceived the concept and designed the analysis; analyzed and interpreted the data. Wrote the paper.

Isaac Chukwutem Abiodun: Analyzed and interpreted the data. Wrote the paper.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict.

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